

A Depression Detection Model using Deep Learning and Textual Entailment

Manar Elshazly #¹, Mohamed Hassan Haggag #², Soha Ahmed Ehssan #³

Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence

Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt

¹manar.elshazly@gmail.com

²mohamed.haggag@fci.helwan.edu.eg

³dr.soha@fci.helwan.edu.eg

Abstract—Depression detection nowadays is essential to help in supporting depressed people. Detecting emotional disturbance is currently remarkable in people who suffer from depression, and yet for doctors and psychologists to help them in detection. Nowadays, social networks can be utilized to determine depressive content and thus depressed people. To accomplish this, twitter is used to collect the most recent tweets that is related to depression. This is done by PHQ-9 technique that classifies depression into 9 degrees. Each degree is represented by set of words. Using this classification, the model can alert users that need a have a visit to a psychiatrist or ask a psychologist as soon as possible based on their social content. The collected dataset is then trained using deep learning and then experimented with different tweets from the collected dataset to validate the model. In addition, with textual entailment, the model can determine whether the tweet is entailed or not from tweets used in the training phase, and thus will follow the same class. By combining deep learning with textual entailment, our model resulted in an improved and quicker depression detection.

Index Terms—deep learning ; depression detection ; Textual entailment ; PHQ-9 ; Social Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Depression detection is a major public health concern. Depression is the head problem of disability and contributes significantly to a load of disease worldwide. People with depression may have a lack of interest and happiness in daily activities, weight loss or heavy gain, insomnia or excessive sleep, lack of energy, inability to concentrate, feelings of worthlessness or guilt and recurring thoughts of death (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). As a matter of fact, depression can lead to suicide. Over 800.000 suicide deaths occur every year and it is the second leading cause of death in the 15-29 years-old range; that is, every 40 s a person dies due to suicide somewhere in the world (World Health Organization, 2014). In wealthier nations, men are three times more likely to commit suicide than women. Globally, suicides account for 50% all violent deaths in men and 71% in women (World Health Organization, 2014). Suicide accounted for close to 1.5% of all deaths worldwide, bringing it into the top 20 leading causes of death in 2015 (World Health Organization, 2017). In the United States, as well as in other high-income countries, suicide is among the 10 leading causes of death (along with cancer, heart disease, stroke, and diabetes),

additionally, from 2016 to 2017 the suicide rate increased by 3.7% (National Center for Health Statistics, 2019). As divided depression level into three classes as represents in [1]. This model also separate depression classes to the same levels but at [1] they decided those levels depending only 100 words they detected them from users tweets they supposed these words based on Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) but in Our model more than 1000 words based on recent PHQ-9 as will be described later.

This paper contributes new dataset of depressed user using PHQ-9 that were collected during the last year with all nowadays problems and depressed reasons. It also proposes a high performance classification model using deep learning techniques which facilitate massive data training . Also, the paper contributes a novel textual entailment depression detection process that helps to extract the depression level for new tweets without re-classifying data.

The rest of paper was split as the following: Section II presenting literature review about depression detection models that used deep learning technique. section III explains the different parts of the proposed model . Section IV discusses experimental results and the evaluation of the proposed model. Finally, the conclusion and future direction and enhancements are discussed in section V.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

In textual entailment deep learning techniques are becoming gradually usable, exceeding the complexity of standard models with complex precision and imagination. In a neural network, deep learning turn into a widespread technique of machine learning due to the state-of-the-art accommodation of computer vision, speech recognition, and other areas[2]. Training huge datasets are the latest fulfillment, from images classification for object recognition to suitable machine translation texts. In spite of this information being now is widely available in the public domain, private information collected on an individual basis not only expands the motivation of current models but also provides new deep learning enhancements. Considering deep learning as the leading technology with the latest applications. Deep learning of successful activities that immediately identify text, image, or sound can be learned with

computer models. Deep learning models achieved higher accuracies that sometimes exceeded human-level performance[3]. Bi-directional GRU (Bi-GRU) is an extension to GRU and is proven suitable for lexical analysis task, in which the input is an entire sentence. Thus, it is important to have the future encoded as well as the history. In particular, a reversed direction GRU is combined with a forward GRU to form a Bi-GRU layer. These two GRUs take the same input but train in different directions, and concatenate their results as output. Deep, hierarchical neural networks can be efficient at representing some functions and modeling varying-length dependencies. Therefore, stacking multiple Bi-GRUs to form a deep network becomes an inevitable choice for improving the representation capability[4].

The repeating bidirectional Gated Recurrent unit is first used as a word-level encoder to capture the context information of the annotations. GRU is a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) that can capture sequence information and sentence dependencies over a long period. Only two reset gate functions are used and upgrade the gates. The renewal gate monitored the rate of data of the previous session that is transferred to the current session. The higher the value of the update gate, the higher the status of the prior build-up. The reset gate monitored the extent to which previous data of the ignored status. When the value of the reset gate is low, the context will be overlooked. Both previous and next texts influence the current word in consecutive texts. Where [5] was used GRU and its results exceeded the LSTM model by 0.03% and it explained that GRU is more specified than LSTM with true negative rate. And as mentioned in [6] only based RNN models is suitable for processing data sequence in their dataset such as GRU and LSTM. So the BiGRU model was used to exclude contextual features. GRU was used to get text and classify it in [7]. GRU was get high performance with text with random sample of classification depression tweets by good accuracy that was 76%. As in [8] they used BI-GRU to encode pattern of texts and it raised accuracy to +80%. Also [9] used the Bi-GRU to get users' tweets, and then use it for classifying user tweets. Where it got reasonable accuracy with 76.4%. The same technique is already used in [10] as an investigation the validity of a claim given based on matters relating to prior verification. That also significantly increased the preceding accuracy.

PHQ-9 is a questionnaire that is a multidisciplinary tool for diagnosing, monitoring, screening, and evaluating the severity of stress. PHQ-9 incorporates the DSM-IV (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders) diagnosis of depression and other vital depressive symptoms into a short reporting tool. The tool measures the frequency of the symbols that are included in the point size index. Question 9 on PHQ-9 screens of presence and duration of suicidal idea¹. The follow-up question, which does not score points on PHQ-9 screens and provides weight to the extent to which stressful issues

have affected the patient's performance level. Model [11] was used GRU to predict the score of PHQ-9 to detect depression of pre-collected dataset by DAIC-corpora 2019, where using more than one of deep learning classification model such as CNN and LSTM with development set score 0.696 and testing set score 0.497 and they aim to use so much complicated techniques to enhance their results in the future. Models [12], [1], and [13] are used lexical similarity techniques to collect words for classification. After researching most papers didn't entailment concept where our model used it to facilitate classification and detect direct the level of depression. We proposed semantic similarity models to determine from which tweet with which level that the input tweet was.

III. PROPOSED MODEL

We depicted a literature review analysis in [14] and researched many related works done in the depression detection using machine learning and deep learning. We concluded that using textual entailment with deep learning can enhance the detection. So, this research a novel model that use deep learning and textual entailment is proposed. Fig.1. shows the framework of our proposed model which begins with collecting dataset using PHQ-9, then altering users with high depressive content. Then, the deep learning is used in the classification of depression levels, and finally textual entailment is applied. All of these steps will be described briefly in the following subsections.

Fig. 1. Depression detection model with entailment

¹<https://pdf4pro.com/view/the-patient-health-questionnaire-phq-9-overview-4c0057.html>

A. Data Collection

The dataset was collected from twitter using tweepy depending on depression lexicon represents in Fig 2. This lexicon was mapped using PHQ-9(the Patient Health Questionnaire-9) technology that is a questionnaire about depression and its levels. This questionnaire is formulated with words and terms defined by psychiatry experts. PHQ-9 technique determined the extent of a person’s depression that is divided into 9 signals. We used more than 1000 words or terms and the model has collected a massive dataset suitable for deep learning. Some lexicon that used in collecting our data are represented in Table I.

Fig. 2. Data Collection Using PHQ-9

Recent tweets were gathered within the period from 23/07/2021 to 04/08/2021, 150 tweets per word or term. The

TABLE I
SOME PHQ-9 WORDS THAT WAS USED IN DATA COLLECTION

Depression Level	PHQ Signal	Symptoms of PHQ-9	Some Words of each Signal
Low	PHQ 0	Lost of interest	lack of joy,lost desire, no joy,no purpose, fed up,no motivation, hiding sadness,zero passion
	PHQ 1	Hopeless and feeling down	being lonely,bad day, breaking down,cry, day ruined,destroyed, disappointed,feeling blue, I am sad
	PHQ 2	Sleep Disturbance	active at night,awake, sleep loss,groggy, night owl,let me sleep, over slept,hibernate
Medium	PHQ 3	Lost of energy	did nothing, exhausted, feeling tired, laziness, sedentary, tired, weakness,motionless
	PHQ 4	Eating Disturbance	big tummy, binge eating, chunky, cut down on fat, dieting, feeling chubby, poor appetite, weighty
	PHQ 5	Let yourself down	I am useless,despicable, ignored,I am nobody, feel ashamed,loser, repulsion,worthless
High	PHQ 6	Concentrating Trouble	absent-minded, daydreamer, disturbed, lase focus, mindless, overthinking, unfocused, zone out
	PHQ 7	Laziness or Hyperactivity	anxiety,angry,annoyed, hysteric,stressed out, panic ,poky,restless, straggler ,unsteady
	PHQ 8	Death Wish or Suicide	better be dead,cut my life, deathly,deserve to die, harm myself, lifeless, kill myself , suicide

Model uses regular expression to remove retweets, special characters, websites’ links and keep only words and numbers. Then it returned all of tweets with username and date for each tweet in a cleaned dataset.

As in [15] PHQ-9 has 9 categories, in our model we re-categorized them into three categories. Low level category that includes (PHQ0 to PhQ2) , Medium level category that includes (PHQ3 to PHQ5) , and High level category that includes (PHQ6 to PHQ8). This new categorization is used for the first part of the model. After editing and filtering the dataset, and removing duplicate tweets the dataset’s size reached 67000 distinct records.

B. High depression user alert

In this step, the model groups tweets by user so that all tweets of each user is categorized using the three categories mentioned in the previous subsection.So, the model takes the name of this user and collects all the tweets that have high level depressive content and if the number of tweets contains more than five high depressed tweets, the system collects the names of all these Users in a new Dictionary. The system then

send an alert message to those users to visit a psychiatrist as soon as possible.

Fig. 3. Extract depressed user by making dictionary of names

Fig. 4. Classification Using Deep learning

C. Deep Learning Classification

To overcome the complexity of various traditional models with complex settings and views, deep learning techniques are becoming very popular in the textual entailment process. Deep learning in neural networks has become a popular method of machine learning due to the recent success of computer vision, speech recognition, and other areas. The latest success is in training large datasets, from object recognition for classified images and machine translation texts. While such information is widely available from public sources, personal data collected from humans not only enhances existing applications but also extends new motivation for deep learning. High accuracy can be accomplished in deep learning applications, sometimes beating human-level achievements.

BI-LSTM: LSTM represents short-term memory networks, used in the Deep Learning field. A variety of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) can learn long-term dependence, especially in consecutive prediction problems. When LSTM works in both directions it is called BI-LSTM [16]. **BI-GRU:** Bi-GRU [8] edgecontains advanced forward GRU and background GRU which are used, respectively, to process forward and

backward data . Deep learning has become popular in the textual entailment scope, conquering the elaboration of several ordinary models with complex ideas. In this work we used two deep learning techniques, GRU and LSTM and their bidirectional models.

First, the categories are mapped into numbers from 0 to 3 to where 0 is neutral, 1 is low , 2 is medium and 3 is high. The data is splitted into three parts: training, testing, and validation. Model put tweet into X and category into Y. Then, X is tokenized into words followed by padding into vertex to prepare it to be input the deep learning models.

This model applied GRU, and Bidirectional GRU [9], LSTM, and LSTM [17] .These mechanisms were noticed to obtain depression tweets, which the model then used for depression classification.

D. Textual Entailment

Recognition of textual entailment sometimes is called inference of natural language. That is the task of determining the distribution of two pieces of text that the translation of one

text can be translated into another text[18]. The relationship-connected action, sometimes three connections can occur between two sentences, is textual entailment. Entailed is the meaning of one sentence can be collective with another sentence, Not Entailed is the meaning of one text that disagrees with the meaning of another sentence, and the Neutral is the meaning of another text that does not add or contradict the meaning of another sentence. Or maybe divided into two categories (Entailed / Neutral)[19].

1) *Entailment using Lexical Similarity*: Lexical similarity has many famous techniques . We used the following methods to take entailment decision by calculating distance similarity between T,H in each one , then calculated the sim(T,H) after that depending on their results to take lexical decision [20]..

- 1) Shapira and sorter's greedy edit distance method has two significant characteristics than other edit distance algorithms. It considers characters blocks if it appears in both text and hypothesis strings, so the editing distance between 'abcab' and 'abc' is only 1, as the substring, 'ab' comes from both and can be inserted as 'abc' blocks. Allows three editing functions: add, delete, and move (but not replace). So the distance between 'abcde' and 'deabc' is only 1 because the 'abc' block can be moved to 1 movement function, rather than removed and placed in 2 different functions. If the key is set to True at startup, this uses a greedy algorithm, which limits block switching to two strings with the same LCS matching .
- 2) BI-SIM similarity:it is based on n-gram, based on measuring the distance similarity.Where n-gram calculated by the following equations. when sequences of words are as in the equation 1 Probabilities of these words presented in equation 2 and bi-gram of these probabilities from equation 3 ,So n-gram probabilities likes equation 4

$$w_1^n = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n \quad (1)$$

$$p(w_1^n) = p(w_1), p(w_2|w_1), p(w_3|w_1^2) \dots p(w_n|w_1^{n-1}) \quad (2)$$

$$p(w_1^n) = \prod_{k=1}^n p(w_k|w_{k-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$p(w_1^n) = \prod_{k=1}^n p(w_k|w_{k-n+1}^{k-1}) \quad (4)$$

- 3) Cosine similarity : Cosine similarity between two text computed from equation 5

$$sim_{cosine}(T,H) = \frac{|T \cap H|}{\sqrt{|T| \cdot |H|}} \quad (5)$$

- 4) normalized eudex hamming :it restores the normal range of Hamming between Eudex hashes for two words or texts.
- 5) SSK : String subsequence kernel (SSK) similarity. All that can follow is the vectors of the feature and the kernel includes their dot product as in the equation 6

$$k_{normalization}(T,H) = \frac{k(T,H)}{\sqrt{k(T,T) * k(H,H)}} \quad (6)$$

2) *Entailment using Semantic Similarity*: we just use two semantic similarity.

- 1) Sentence-Transformers-Bert:It puts a map of the sentences and paragraphs in the 768 density vector and can be used for tasks such as merging or semantic search [21].BERT uses a cross-encoder.it passed two sentences to network and then predict value of similarity.
- 2) Spacy:it depends on estimating semantic similarity. Estimated cosine similarity using the word vector measurement[22].

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

After collecting the dataset it is saved as csv containing 67161 distinct records , each record has User names, Date of tweet, Tweet's content , and level of depression depending on PHQ-9 lexicon , Table II represents sample of collected dataset.

TABLE II
COLLECTED DATASET SAMPLE

user name	date	tweet	level
User1	08/02/21 10:32 AM	You can t tell me that the lack of joy comes from a country so divided that half of the idiotic population	low
User2	08/02/21 10:59 AM	I thought Joy came in the morning Well it s the morning and there s no joy in my life What s all that about huh	low
User3	08/04/21 11:51 AM	Man I can t never decide what I want to eat Tired of eating everything really	medium
User4	07/28/21 06:28 PM	anuraax feeling like a loser actually	medium
User5	08/04/21 11:58 AM	another dr apt today another day filled with anxiety and ptsd triggers	high
User6	08/01/21 06:01 PM	But I knew what I had to do I have to kill myself	high

The model is evaluated using Accuracy from Eq.7 which is mean to number of correct prediction to number of total dataset as described before in [12]. From equation 8 and equation 9 Precision and Recall which is computed to get F1 Score as described in equation 10.Where TP are true positives, TN are true negatives, FP is false positives and FN are false negatives as mentioned in [23].

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (8)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (9)$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (10)$$

when applying GRU , LSTM and Bi-directional models to our dataset, BI-GRU got the best results. We trained, tested, and validated our dataset with a batch size equals to 500 , no. of epochs =20 ,drop out size of any network = 0.4 ,vocabulary size that we applied our models on it was 5000 , with 32

hidden layer for every DL model , and finally embedding size was equaled to 60. Evaluation splitting parameter was testing on 90%,80%,70% for training with dividing equally the remaining for testing and validation.

The results showed that the 90% splitting was stable and better than two other splitting parameters fig 5 depending on the best Accuracy for each model within 20 epochs.GRU, BI-GRU, LSTM,and ending with BI-LSTM got 0.8195, 0.8240 , 0.8160, and 0.8248 respectively.These results are represented in figures Fig 6.,Fig 7. , Fig8. , Fig 9.

Fig. 5. Evaluation Splitting Parameters(Accuracy)

Fig. 6. Accuracy Using GRU training by 90%

Finally our evaluation of the deep learning step in the proposed model is mentioned in Table III .Accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score is presented for each model separately but only for the best evaluation splitting as mentioned before 90% for training ,5% testing, and also 5% validation.

TABLE III
MODELS EVALUATIONS COMPARISON

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
GRU	0.8094	0.8492	0.7774	0.8117
BI-GRU	0.8182	0.8294	0.8091	0.8192
LSTM	0.8055	0.8101	0.8025	0.8063
BI-LSTM	0.8132	0.8194	0.8085	0.8139

After classification, the entailment process is followed. We tried two types of textual entailment, lexical similarity and

Fig. 7. Accuracy Using Bi-GRU training by 90%

Fig. 8. Accuracy Using LSTM training by 90%

Fig. 9. Accuracy Using BI-LSTM training by 90%

semantic similarity. which proved that the semantic similarity gives reasonable decision near to expert detection.Table IV contains some of classified collected tweets by deep learning as (Text) and the new tweets to be classified as (Hypothesis). Table V represents entailment decisions of the sample pairs in tableIV using lexical techniques. We tried different types of lexical methods, and the results were quite similar, so we took average of five lexical similarity techniques that was

mentioned in the proposed model to get the best realistic results. For semantic similarity, we used two famous similarity measure semantic similarity Spacy and sentence-transformer-BERT separately.

TABLE IV
TEXT (CLASSIFIED TWEETS BY DEEP LEARNING) AND
HYPOTHESIS(TWEETS TO BE CLASSIFIED BY TEXTUAL ENTAILMENT)
EXAMPLES

No.	Text	Hypothesis
1	being alone for a while is dangerous it s addicting once you see how peaceful it is you don t want to deal with people any	major play people who dislike this song are against joy and happiness idc this such mood lifter helped much when depression started
2	Let s not equate a rise in COVID cases with people dying Feeling crappy for 2 days isn t worth compromising your freedom	the lancet normal anxiety and depression works negatively your immune system thats why they scare for virus equal flue
3	2am Hearing cries of the children amp firing like fire crackers in the background as I talk to a friend	gavinnewsom can you speed for teachers and get our kids back school please the depression surging especially for teens
4	coldfallout Let me say it plain I loved someone and I failed at it Let me say it another way I like to call myself wound but I will	toxic relationship the lockdown because covid pandemic also had devastating effect relationships the sudden inactivities and depression brought out the beast some people and many found themselves toxic relationship
5	ageingacf older adults are at increased risk for loneliness and social isolation because they are more likely to be living alone espec	depression keeps from playing guitar and every time come back around like playing again for the first time

$$Entdecision(T, H) = \begin{cases} Entailed & \text{if } Sim(T, H) \geq \sigma \\ NotEntailed & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

TABLE V
ENTAILED DECISION

Text	Hypothesis	Lexical	sentence-transformers/ bert-base	Spacy
<i>Text</i> ₁	<i>Hypothesis</i> ₁	Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
<i>Text</i> ₂	<i>Hypothesis</i> ₂	Not Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
<i>Text</i> ₃	<i>Hypothesis</i> ₃	Not Entailed	Entailed	Entailed
<i>Text</i> ₄	<i>Hypothesis</i> ₄	Not Entailed	Not Entailed	Entailed
<i>Text</i> ₅	<i>Hypothesis</i> ₅	Entailed	Entailed	Entailed

V. CONCLUSION

With the current pressures of life, the rate of depression and anxiety in society was noticeably increasing. Thus, the percentage of posts and tweets on social networking sites with depressive contents increases as well. Therefore, there is a need for an efficient depression detection from textual social content. After researching similar studies, we found that textual entailment is promising when using with deep learning

as proposed in this research.

This work presents a new dataset collected using the latest underwriting words developed using PHQ-9. Four deep learning models were tested, GRU, Bi-GRU, LSTM, and BI-LSTM. BI-GRU had the best results and the accuracy rate was above 80%. Finally, the model used the textual entailment process to find out which of the classified tweets are similar to the new ones to find out their depression level without the need of reclassification using deep learning. Also, it helps in online detection for new tweets without the need of retraining. This is a quite novel combined model that enhance the performance of depression detection in terms of time. Also, considering textual entailment, the paper concludes that the semantic entailment is much better than lexical entailment when dealing with social text content.

In future work, we aim to increase our dataset and combine different deep learning methods for better detection. Also, we aim to take emojis into consideration in the preprocessing process. This work can be also extended by working on different social domains. Finally, working on Arabic content is one of our future directions.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. U. Mustafa, N. Ashraf, F. S. Ahmed, J. Ferzund, B. Shahzad, and A. Gelbukh, "A multiclass depression detection in social media based on sentiment analysis," in *Proceedings of the 17th IEEE International Conference on Information Technology—New Generations*. Springer, 2020, pp. 659–662.
- [2] T. Khot, A. Sabharwal, and P. Clark, "Scitail: A textual entailment dataset from science question answering," in *Thirty-Second AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2018.
- [3] S. Gupta, S. Lakra, and M. Kaur, "Sentiment analysis using partial textual entailment," in *2019 International Conference on Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud and Parallel Computing (COMITCon)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 51–55.
- [4] Z. Jiao, S. Sun, and K. Sun, "Chinese lexical analysis with deep bi-gru-crf network," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.01882*, 2018.
- [5] N. Gruber and A. Jockisch, "Are gru cells more specific and lstm cells more sensitive in motive classification of text?" *Frontiers in artificial intelligence*, vol. 3, p. 40, 2020.
- [6] S. G. Burdisso, M. Errecalde, and M. Montes-y Gómez, "A text classification framework for simple and effective early depression detection over social media streams," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 133, pp. 182–197, 2019.
- [7] T. Gui, L. Zhu, Q. Zhang, M. Peng, X. Zhou, K. Ding, and Z. Chen, "Cooperative multimodal approach to depression detection in twitter," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 33, no. 01, 2019, pp. 110–117.
- [8] D. Chen, Y. Li, M. Yang, H.-T. Zheng, and Y. Shen, "Knowledge-aware textual entailment with graph attention network," in *Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management*, 2019, pp. 2145–2148.
- [9] H. Zogan, I. Razzak, X. Wang, S. Jameel, and G. Xu, "Explainable depression detection with multi-modalities using a hybrid deep learning model on social media," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.02847*, 2020.
- [10] A. Bidgoly, H. Amirkhani, and F. Sadeghi, "Fake news detection on social media using a natural language inference approach," *Research Square*, 2020.
- [11] M. Rodrigues Makiuchi, T. Warnita, K. Uto, and K. Shinoda, "Multi-modal fusion of bert-cnn and gated cnn representations for depression detection," in *Proceedings of the 9th International on Audio/Visual Emotion Challenge and Workshop*, 2019, pp. 55–63.
- [12] M. M. Tadesse, H. Lin, B. Xu, and L. Yang, "Detection of depression-related posts in reddit social media forum," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 44 883–44 893, 2019.

- [13] F. M. Shah, F. Ahmed, S. K. S. Joy, S. Ahmed, S. Sadek, R. Shil, and M. H. Kabir, "Early depression detection from social network using deep learning techniques," in *2020 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYMP)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 823–826.
- [14] M. Elshazly, M. Haggag, and S. A. Ehssan, "Natural language processing applications: A new taxonomy using textual entailment," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2021.0120580>
- [15] D. Li, H. Chaudhary, and Z. Zhang, "Modeling spatiotemporal pattern of depressive symptoms caused by covid-19 using social media data mining," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 14, p. 4988, 2020.
- [16] S. Evensen, Y. Suhara, A. Halevy, V. Li, W.-C. Tan, and S. Mumick, "Happiness entailment: Automating suggestions for well-being," in *2019 8th International Conference on Affective Computing and Intelligent Interaction (ACII)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 62–68.
- [17] A. Sherstinsky, "Fundamentals of recurrent neural network (rnn) and long short-term memory (lstm) network," *Physica D: Nonlinear Phenomena*, vol. 404, p. 132306, 2020.
- [18] S. H. Jayasinghe and K. Sirts, "Deep learning textual entailment system for sinhala language," 2019.
- [19] P. Kapanipathi, V. Thost, S. S. Patel, S. Whitehead, I. Abdelaziz *et al.*, "Infusing knowledge into the textual entailment task using graph convolutional networks," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 34, no. 05, 2020, pp. 8074–8081.
- [20] C. C. Little, "Abydos documentation," 2018.
- [21] N. Reimers and I. Gurevych, "Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks," in *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Association for Computational Linguistics, 11 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084>
- [22] "Spacy v3.2 spacy for semantic similarity," <https://spacy.io/api/docsimilarity>, accessed: 2021-10-30.
- [23] S. A. E. Aly, A. Hassanin, and S. Bekhet, "Esldl: An integrated deep learning model for egyptian sign language recognition," in *2021 3rd Novel Intelligent and Leading Emerging Sciences Conference (NILES)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 331–335.